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1. Executive summary

GUTTA project’s external communication is based on stakeholder’s engagement. They include both Institutions, academic organizations, and private actors. In order to target the most relevant stakeholders, a database is prepared and maintained by the GUTTA consortium. It can be used for invitation to GUTTA public events and for dissemination of project results. This report includes a snapshot of the database, with contact person information obscured for protecting privacy.

2. Database structure

The stakeholders’ database (hereafter called “SDB”) consists in an Excel file organized into several sheets. Each sheet contains data relative to a specific stakeholder category, as listed in Sect.2.1. Furthermore, for each entry of the SDB, the fields of Sect.2.2. are filled, when available.

2.1. SDB Categories

	Number of entries
Academia	43
Institutions	92
Industry	104
Sectoral Agencies	103
Total	342
Total unique emails	329

2.2. SDB Fields

- Surname
- Name
- Organization
- Country
- Topics
- role
- email
- telephone

3. Database screenshots

3.1 Academia

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Surname	Name	Organization	role	Country	email
2			Politecnico of Bari	IT	Environmental and Maritime Hydraulics	
3						
4			Unisalento	IT	autonomous underwater vehicles	
5			CNR-ISAC	IT	particulate matter	
6			Politecnico Bari	IT	operation research	
7			Politecnico Bari	IT		
8			UniParthenope	IT	grid, cloud, mobile computing	
9			UBO	FR	marine mammals	
10			CNR-ISAC	IT	particulate matter	
11			University of Genoa	IT	naval architecture	
12			University of Trieste	IT	naval architecture	
13			University of Trieste	IT	naval architecture	
14			University of Salento	IT	wild law	
15			Uni Venezia	IT	operation research	
16			Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (BarcelonaTECH	ES	ports, energy, ship routing	
17						
18			Pomorski fakultet u Rijeci	Croatia		
19			Pomorski fakultet u Rijeci	Croatia		
20			Ekonomski fakultet u Rijeci	Croatia		
21			Ekonomski fakultet u Rijeci	Croatia		
22			Ekonomski fakultet u Rijeci	Croatia		
23						
24			Pomorski fakultet u Rijeci	Croatia	Dean	
25			Pomorski fakultet u Splitu	Croatia	Dean	
26			Prometni fakultet u Zagrebu	Croatia	Dean	
27			Sveučilište u Dubrovniku	Croatia	Rector	
28			Sveučilište u Dubrovniku, Pomorski odjel	Croatia	Head	
29			Pomorski fakultet u Rijeci	Croatia	Head	
30						
31			Technical school Blaž Jurjev Trogiranin	Croatia	Technical	
32			Franciscan classical gymnasium in Sinj	Croatia	Classical gymnasium	
33			High School	Croatia	High School	
34			ITS/GIS/GPS education	Croatia	ITS/GIS/GPS education	
35			High Education	Croatia	Academy of Dramatic Art University of Zagreb	
36			Higher education	Serbia	The Faculty of Philosophy University of Novi Sad	
37			Hotel-tourism and hospitality school Zadar	Croatia	Hotels, Tourism	
38			University of Zagreb Faculty of Textile Technology	Croatia	Textile technology	
39			University of Rijeka Faculty of Economics	Croatia	Economy	
40			University of Zagreb Faculty of Economics	Croatia	Economy	
41			University of Juraj Dobrila in Pula Faculty of Economics and tou	Croatia	economy, tourism	
42			University of Josip Juraj Strossmayer in Osijek Faculty of Philos	Croatia	philosophy	
43			Economics Bureau and Technical School Zadar	Croatia	economics, technical	
44			University of Zagreb Faculty of Teacher Educationc	Croatia	Teacher Education	
45			Zadar technical school	Croatia	Director	
46			Maritime School of Zadar	Cratia	Director	
47			Faculty of Maritime, Split	Croatia	Dean	
48			Public open college Libar	Croatia	Training Manager	
49						
50						

3.2 Institutions

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Surname	Name	Organization	role	Country	email
2			Apulia Region	IT	PP.OO. F.E.S.R.	
3			Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure- Coast Guard	IT	Chief	
4			Customs	IT	Director	
5			Border Police	IT	Director	
6			Guardia di Finanza	IT	Colonel	
7						
8			Capitanerie di porto	IT	commander	
9			Capitanerie di porto	IT	commander	
10			ARPA-Puglia	IT	dirigente	
11			Avvisatori Marittimi Brindisi	IT	dirigente	
12				Montenegro	Deputy Director at Maritime Safety Department	
13			Bahamas Maritime Authority		Deputy Director Maritime Affairs	
14			Ministry of Justice	IT	Procuratore	
15			NATO-CMRE	IT		
16			JRC Ispra	IT		
17			ISPRA Roma	IT		
18			Greentech Cluster Emilia Romagna	IT	Innovation Manager	
19			Regione Puglia	IT	Funzionario Tecnico	
20			SASEMAR	ES	Simulator developer	
21			Provincia di Lecce	IT	Dirigente Servizio Politiche Comunitarie Sviluppo Locale	
22			Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare	IT		
23			Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare	IT		
24			Comune di Lecce	IT	Dirigente Programmazione strategica, Europa e cooperazione, patrimoni	
25						
26						
27						
28						
29						
30			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia	Minister	
31			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia	Assistant Minister	
32			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia	Assistant Minister	
33			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia	State Secretary	
34			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia	Sector Chief	
35			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia		
36			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia		
37			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia		
38			Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure	Croatia	Scientist	
39			Ministry of Regional Development and EU Funds	Croatia		
40			Ministry of Regional Development and EU Funds	Croatia	Head of Department for CBC Programme Italy – Croatia and IPA ADRIATI	
41			Ministry of Regional Development and EU Funds	Croatia	First Level Control	
42			Office for Cooperation with NGOs	Croatia	Senior Expert Advisor	
43			Office for Cooperation with NGOs	Croatia		
44						
45			Klipper - Ustanova za obrazovanje kadrova u pomorstvu	Croatia	Director	
46			Suvremeno učilište u Splitu – Pomorsko učilište Atlantis	Croatia	Director	
47			Pomorsko otvoreno učilište Božić	Croatia	Director	
48			Adria Libar d.o.o. (Šibenik)	Croatia	Director	
49			Advanced Maritime Venture d.o.o.	Croatia	Director	
50			Brodsko upravljanje d.o.o.	Croatia	Director	

3.3 Industry

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Surname	Name	Organization	role	Country	email
2			A.L.A	IT		
3			Albini e Pittigliani	IT		
4			ARTONI export	IT		
5			CEVA	IT		
6			GEFCO Italia	IT		
7			GEODIS	IT		
8			GTS	IT		
9			Hartrodt	IT		
10			Log Service Distribution	IT		
11			C.I.L.T. Consorzio Imballaggisti in Le	IT		
12			CARTOPLAST TRADE srl	IT		
13			CTV srl	IT		
14			FIDANZIA SISTEMI srl	IT		
15			FLASH-PACK	IT		
16			GREENFILL di Omar Granatelli	IT		
17			ICMI srl	IT		
18			LAZIALE DISTRIBUZIONE srl	IT		
19			MBL Solutions srl	IT		
20			PROPACK SpA	IT		
21			SERPAC srl	IT		
22						
23			Marine Traffic	GR	R&D responsabile	
24			CTI Patras	GR	Prof	
25			Planetek Italia	IT	CEO	
26			consorzio906	IT		
27			consorzio906	IT		
28			Dappolonia	IT		
29			Dappolonia	IT		
30			Wartsila	IT	Manager, Noise & Vibration	
31			Wartsila	IT	Communication Manager	
32			MICAD	IT	CEO	
33			Grimaldi Group	IT	Dept. Energy saving	
34			Piloti del Porto di Livorno	IT		
35			RINA	IT		
36			RINA	IT	Smart Monitoring, Project Manager	
37			Lucia	ES		
38			Stena	NL		
39			RINA	IT	maritime and logistics, Technical Leader	
40			CMB	BE		
41			Focus	IT		
42			SeaPlace	ES		
43			Leonardo, IET	IT		
44			DNV GL	IT		
45			Trinity House London licensed Nort	HR		
46			Jadrolinija	HR		
47						
48			Fishing Industry-Omega 3	Croatia	Director	
49			Fishing Industry-Cromaris d.o.o.	Croatia	Director	
50						

3.4 Sectoral Agencies

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Surname	Name	Organization	role	Country	email
2			BARI SHIPPING		IT	
3			BLUMARE		IT	
4			DISCOVERY SHIPPING		IT	
5			DOLPHINS		IT	
6			MORFIMARE		IT	
7			P.SANTELIA		IT	
8			PORTTRANS		IT	
9			SEAMED TRADING SHIPPING S.R.L.		IT	
10			SPAMAT		IT	
11			TITI SHIPPING BARI		IT	
12						
13			Orca	activist	UK	
14			Souffleurs d'ecume	activist	FR	
15			WWF	activist	FR	
16			Lega Navale Regionale		IT	
17			Lega Navale Regionale		IT	
18						
19			Public Institution Natura Jadera	Director	Croatia	
20			Institution for Competence Development, In	Director	Croatia	
21			Conservation department	Head of Depar	Croatia	
22			Translation agency Lingua soft Ltd	Branch Repres	Croatia	
23			Public institution National park Northern Vel	Director	Croatia	
24			Public institution ZadarCounty Development	Director	Croatia	
25						
26			PORT AUTHORITY RIJEKA	Director	Croatia	
27			PORT AUTHORITY ZADAR	Director	Croatia	
28			PORT AUTHORITY ŠIBENIK	Director	Croatia	
29			PORT AUTHORITY SPLIT	Director	Croatia	
30			PORT AUTHORITY PLOČE	Director	Croatia	
31			PORT AUTHORITY DUBROVNIK	Director	Croatia	
32			PORT AUTHORITY Vukovar	Director	Croatia	
33			PORT AUTHORITY Slavonski brod	Director	Croatia	
34			PORT AUTHORITY Osijek	Director	Croatia	
35			PORT AUTHORITY Sisak	Director	Croatia	
36			PORT OF RIJEKA d.d.	Director	Croatia	
37			PORT OF PULA d.d.	Director	Croatia	
38			PORT OF ZADAR d.d.	Director	Croatia	
39			PORT OF ŠIBENIK d.d.	Director	Croatia	
40			PORT OF SPLIT d.d.	Director	Croatia	
41			PORT OF PLOČE d.d.	Director	Croatia	
42			PORT OF DUBROVNIK d.d.	Director	Croatia	
43						
44			zadarska	Director	Croatia	
45			šibensko-kninske	Director	Croatia	
46			Splitsko-dalmatinske	Director	Croatia	
47			dubrovačko-neretvanske	Director	Croatia	
48			Dubrovnik	Director	Croatia	
49			Umag-Novigrad	Director	Croatia	
50			Rabac	Director	Croatia	

4. Conclusions

A database of more than 300 stakeholders is made available to the GUTTA Consortium. It consists of four stakeholder categories: Academia, Institutions, Industry, Sectoral Agencies. The database size is consistent with the target envisioned by the project's Communication Strategy (cf. Deliverable 2.1.3.).

The database emails have been inserted into the GUTTA dissemination mailing list (gutta-ext@cmcc.it).

All GUTTA partner Organizations contributed to this deliverable. The database is a living document and will be updated and possibly enlarged during the GUTTA project lifetime, in order to provide the most comprehensive information to serve the Communication aims of the project.